

FORMULATION BASED ON ADVANCED ATM FOR LONG-TERM FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF CFRP LAMINATES FOR MARINE USE

Y. Miyano, M. Nakada and H. Cai
Materials System Research Laboratory/ Kanazawa Institute of Technology
3-1 Yatsukaho Hakusan Ishikawa 924-0838, Japan
miyano@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

SUMMARY

The main objectives of this research include: (a) proposing theoretically an advanced accelerated testing methodology (advanced ATM) for the long-term fatigue life prediction of polymer composites on the viewpoint of viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin; (b) verifying experimentally the proposed advanced ATM for CFRP laminates for marine use.

Keywords: Durability, Life prediction, Fatigue, Creep, CFRP, Marine

INTRODUCTION

Previously, authors of this paper have developed an accelerated testing methodology (ATM) to predict the long-term fatigue life of the polymer matrix composites based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) held for the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin [1]. The ATM using the TTSP enables us to describe the long-term life by means of master curves covering wide ranges of loading and environmental conditions, including load duration, temperature, frequency of load cycles, load amplitude ratios, etc. The ATM has been applied for various composites and their joint structures, and demonstrated with a great success as a robust and power methodology for the long-term life prediction. This methodology can be applied to the life prediction of polymer composites exposed only to the constant load pattern (load amplitude and frequency) and environmental condition (temperature and water absorption).

In the present paper, we propose an advanced accelerated testing methodology (advanced ATM) which can be applied to the life prediction of polymer composites exposed to an actual load and environment history. First, the four conditions for the advanced ATM are introduced. Second, the long-term fatigue strength of polymer composites exposed to an actual load and environment history is formulated based on the four conditions. Third, the parameters in the formulation are determined for CFRP laminates for marine use. As results, it is verified that the advanced ATM is applicable to the long-term fatigue life prediction of CFRP laminates for marine composites exposed to an actual load and temperature history.

ADVANCED ATM

The advanced ATM is established with four following conditions: (A) the same TTSP is applicable for both non-destructive viscoelastic behavior and destructive strength properties of matrix resin and their composites; (B) strength variation is caused by viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin; (C) failure probability is independent of time, temperature, frequency and stress ratio; (D) strength degradation is caused by linear cumulative damage of cyclic loading.

A key component of the advanced ATM is also the empirical observation (A), which has been demonstrated its applicability for various polymeric composite materials and their structures. Based on the condition (A), the master curves of constant strain rate (CSR), creep and fatigue strengths in the wide range of time and temperature can be determined by the data measured by these tests under the short-term and elevated temperature conditions. With the condition (B), it is possible to calculate the strength variation by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin determined by the creep compliance of matrix resin and the history of load and temperature changed with time. With the condition (C), the reference strength and the failure probability can be obtained by measuring CSR strength at an arbitrary strain rate under room temperature. With the condition (D), it is possible to calculate the strength degradation by load cycles undergoing to the linear cumulative damage law. The formulation for long-term fatigue strength of polymer composites exposed to an actual load and environment history are conducted under the four conditions of advanced ATM.

The procedure for determining the materials parameters in the formulation of the advanced ATM is illustrated in Figure 1. First, the change in modulus or compliance of viscoelastic matrix resin is measured over time at a constant temperature. The tests are repeated for several elevated temperatures, which results in several modulus or compliance curves with the function of time. The time-temperature shift factor are then determined by shifting the viscoelastic modulus or compliance curves at the several temperatures into time scale to form a master curve of the modulus or compliance at a reference temperature. The time-temperature shift factor is thus the measure of the acceleration of the life of matrix resin by means of the elevated temperatures. The next step is to obtain the creep strength master curves. This step consists of two parts. The first part is to determine CSR strength master curve of the composites from the CSR loading tests conducted at a single strain rate and several elevated temperatures using the time-temperature shift factor for matrix resin, and the second part is to convert CSR strength master curve to the creep strength master curve of the composites. Third, the master curves of fatigue strength of the composites at zero stress ratio are determined by conducting the fatigue tests at several stress levels, a single frequency, stress ratio (zero stress ratio) and temperature using CSR strength master curve. Finally, the master curves of fatigue strength at an arbitrary stress ratio are determined by the creep strength master curve and the fatigue strength master curves at zero stress ratio. Through these procedures, all of materials parameters in the formulations can be determined for the long-term fatigue strength at an arbitrary load condition in which the stress and temperature arbitrarily changed with time.

Figure 1 Procedure of advanced accelerated testing methodology (advanced ATM) for polymer composites

FORMULATION

Long-term fatigue strength of polymer composites under actual loading

The long-term fatigue strength $\sigma_f(t', T_0)$ under actual loading can be formulated based on the four conditions of advanced ATM.

$$\log \sigma_f(t', f', N_f, R) = \log \sigma_s(t'_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log [-\ln(1 - P_f)] - \log \left[\frac{D^*(t', f', R)}{D_c(t'_0)} \right]^{n_r} - \log \left[\frac{N_f}{N_0} / (1 - k_D) \right]^{\frac{(1-R)}{2} \cdot n_f}, \quad (1)$$

where the first term $\sigma_s(t'_0, T_0)$ is the scale parameter of CSR strength measured at an initial reduced time t'_0 at a reference temperature T_0 which is the static strength at glassy state.

The second term shows Weibull distribution of failure probability P_f in which the shape parameter is α . The α is independent of time to failure, temperature, frequency and stress ratio from the condition (C) based on Christensen's theory [2].

The third term shows the variation caused by the viscoelastic compliance D^* of matrix resin defined by the following equation based on the condition (B). The n_r in this term is the parameter to be dependent on the failure mechanism.

$$D^*(t', T_0) = \frac{\varepsilon(t', T_0)}{\sigma(t', T_0)} = \frac{\int_0^{t'} D_c(t' - \tau', T_0) \frac{d\sigma(\tau')}{d\tau'} d\tau'}{\sigma(t', T_0)}, \quad (2)$$

where D_c is the creep compliance of matrix resin. t' is the reduced time at the reference temperature T_0 which is shown by the following equation based on the condition (A).

$$t' = \int_0^t \frac{d\tau}{a_{T_0}(T(\tau))}, \quad (3)$$

where a_{T_0} is the time-temperature shift factor for the creep compliance of matrix resin.

The fourth term shows the degradation caused by cumulative damage of cyclic loading. In this term, N_f and R is the number of cycles to failure and the stress ratio at the final step, respectively. N_0 is the reference number of cycles to failure = 1/2 and n_f is the parameter to be dependent on the failure mechanism. k_D is defined as the following equation based on the condition (D).

$$k_D = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{N_{fi}} < 1, \quad (4)$$

where n_i and N_{fi} are the number of cycles and the number of cycles to failure at the loading of step i , respectively.

Creep compliance of matrix resin

The formulation for the master curve of creep compliance of matrix resin D_c in Equation (1) and the time-temperature shift factor of matrix resin $a_{T_0}(T)$ in Equation (3) should be performed for the long-term fatigue strength of polymer composites under actual loading. The master curve of D_c can be represented by two tangential lines, whose slopes are m_g and m_r , respectively. With these parameters, the master curve of D_c can be fit with the following equation,

$$\log D_c = \log D_c(t'_o, T_0) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_o} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right], \quad (5)$$

where t'_o is an initial reduced time at a reference temperature T_0 . t'_g is the reduced glassy time at a reference temperature T_0 . m_g and m_a are the parameters.

The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ that is the amount of the horizontal shift, can be fit with the following equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \log a_{T_0}(T) = & \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) \\ & + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T_g} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(Kmol)], ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are the activation energies below and above the glass transition temperature T_g , respectively, and H is the Heaviside step function. The temperature shift factor, $b_{T_0}(T)$, which is the amount of the vertical shift, can be fit with the following equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \log b_{T_0}(T) = & b_1(T - T_0) H(T_g - T) \\ & + \left[b_1(T_g - T_0) + b_2(T - T_g) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are slopes of two line segments below and above T_g .

Alternatively, the viscoelastic behaviors of the matrix resin can be represented by the storage modulus E' which can easily be measured with experimental devices such as the dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) conducted at various frequencies and temperatures. Note that D_c can approximately be obtained from E' by using

$$D_c = 1/E'. \quad (8)$$

CSR, creep and fatigue strength of polymer composites

For the CSR strength σ_s , the Equation (1) can be simplified to the following equation,

$$\log \sigma_s = \log \sigma_s(t'_o, T_o) + \frac{1}{\alpha_s} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - \log \left[\frac{D_c(t'/2)}{D_c(t'_o)} \right]^{n_r} \quad (9)$$

For the creep strength σ_c , the Equation (1) can be simplified to the following equation,

$$\log \sigma_c = \log \sigma_s(t'_o, T_o) + \frac{1}{\alpha_s} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - \log \left[\frac{D_c(t')}{D_c(t'_o)} \right]^{n_r}, \quad (10)$$

For the fatigue strength σ_s under cyclic loading which stress ratio R is zero, the Equation (1) can be simplified to the following equations,

$$\log \sigma_f = \log \sigma_{s,o}(t'_o, T_o) + \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - \log \left[\frac{D^*(t', f')}{D_c(t'_o)} \right]^{n_r} - \frac{1}{2} \log \left[\frac{N_f}{N_0} \right]^{n_f}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$D^*(t', f') = \frac{1}{2} D_c(t') + \frac{1}{2} D_c \left(\frac{1}{4f'} \right). \quad (12)$$

LONG-TERM FATIGUE STRENGTH OF CFRP LAMINATES FOR MARINE USE

Determination of all parameters in the formulation for the long-term fatigue strength under actual loading for three kinds of CFRP laminates is explained in this section. Three kinds of CFRP laminates are plain woven T300 carbon fibers fabric/vinylester (T300/VE), plain woven T700 carbon fibers flat fabric/vinylester (T700/VE-F) and multi-axial knitted T700 carbon fibers fabric/vinylester (T700/VE-K) for marine use.

Creep compliance and time-temperature shift factors

The creep compliances of matrix resin at various temperature were measured by the three-point bending creep tests. The storage moduli at various temperatures were also measured by the dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) in order to get the accurate shift factors in the wide range of temperature.

The creep compliances at various temperatures shown in the left of Figure 2 were shifted horizontally and vertically to construct the smooth master curve of creep compliance shown in the right of this figure. The activation energy ΔH_1 in the horizontal time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ shown by Equation (6) and the parameter b_1 in the vertical temperature shift factor $b_{T_0}(T)$ shown by Equation (7) were determined through the construction of creep compliance master curve as shown in Figure 4.

The storage moduli at various temperatures shown in the left of Figure 3 were shifted horizontally and vertically to construct the smooth master curve of storage modulus shown in the right of this figure. The activation energy ΔH_2 , the parameter b_2 and the glass transition temperature T_g in Equations (6) and (7) were determined through the construction of storage modulus master curve.

The material parameters of $D_c(t'_0, T_0)$, t'_g , m_g and m_a in the creep compliance master curve shown by Equation (5) are determined after the reconstruction of creep compliance master curve by shifting horizontally and vertically the creep compliances at various temperatures as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Master curve of creep compliance of matrix resin

Figure 3 Master curve of storage modulus of matrix resin

Figure 4 Master curves of horizontal shift factor and vertical shift factor of matrix resin

Flexural CSR strength of CFRP laminates

The left side of each graph in Figure 5 shows the flexural CSR strength σ_s versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures T for three kinds of CFRP laminates, where t_s is the time period from initial loading to maximum load during testing. The master curves of σ_s versus the reduced time to failure t_s' were constructed by shifting σ_s at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t_s using the same time-temperature shift factors for D_c and E' of matrix resin shown in Figure 4. It is cleared from Figure 5 that the σ_s for all three CFRP laminates strongly decreases with increasing time and temperature.

The flexural CSR strength for three kinds of CFRP laminates were formulated using Equation (9), whose parameters are listed in Table 1. Weibull plots of the CSR strength data are also shown in Figure 5. During the formulation, the parameter n_r was fixed to 0.5 for the micro-buckling failure mechanism.

The formulated curves of CSR strength of all three kinds of CFRP laminates agree well with the experimental data.

Weibull shape parameters α_s in the case that the material parameter n_r is fixed to 0.5 were compared with those in the case that the material parameter n_r as shown in Figure 6. The shape parameters from both methods are very close. Therefore, the CSR strength formulation with fixed n_r is reasonable as the standardized formulation method.

Figure 5 Master curves of flexural CSR strength and Weibull distributions

Figure 6 Comparison of shape parameters α_s with different gradient parameters n_r

Master curves of fatigue strength of CFRP laminates

To construct the master curve of flexural fatigue strength σ_f , we need the reduced frequency f' in addition to the reduced time to failure t_f' defined by the following equations

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T) \quad , \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (13)$$

where N_f is the number of cycles to failure.

S-N curves showing the relations of σ_f and N_f at frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$ at various temperatures were measured for three kinds of CFRP laminates shown in Figure 7. These S-N curves were formulated using the Equation (11). The time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ of the creep compliance of matrix resin was used to convert f and N_f into f' and t_f' for each CFRP laminates. The formulation parameters for fatigue strength of three kinds of CFRP laminates are listed in Table 1. The formulated curves of fatigue strength of all three kinds of CFRP laminates agree well with the experimental data.

Using the formulation parameters, the master curves of fatigue strength versus the reduced time t' for distinct N_f can be constructed as depicted in solid line in Figure 8. It is cleared from Figures 7 and 8 that the σ_f of all three CFRP laminates strongly decreases with time to failure, temperature although the σ_f decreases scarcely with N_f .

The scale parameters σ_s of CSR strength for three kinds of CFRP laminates at an initial reduced time at a reference temperature are clearly different from each other, as shown on Table 1, because the carbon fibers and weave structure are different. The shape parameters α_s and α_f of both CSR and fatigue strengths, the formulation parameters n_r and n_f have approximately the same values for three kinds of CFRP laminates. The n_f is very small. From these facts that the failure mechanism is the same for these CFRP laminates and the degradation of these fatigue strengths is controlled by matrix resin. The effect of number of load cycles on the flexural strength of these CFRP laminates is negligible small.

Figure 7 S-N curves at various temperatures and Weibull distributions

Table 1 Formulation parameters of three kinds of CFRP laminates

	T_0 [°C]	25		
	t_0' [min]	1		
	$D_{c0}(t_0', T_0)$ [1/GPa]	0.287		
	m_g	0.0003		
Resin	m_r	0.455		
	t'_g at T_0 [min]	1.50×10^6		
	ΔH_1 [KJ/mol]	146.4		
	ΔH_2 [KJ/mol]	648.7		
	T_g [°C]	109		
			T300/VE	T700/VE-F
	$\sigma_s(t_0', T_0)$	652	1061	951
	α_s	6.7	5.8	5.4
	α_f	5.6	8.1	5.2
CFRP	n_r	0.5	0.5	0.5
	n_f	0.028	0.038	0.033

CONCLUSIONS

The advanced accelerated testing methodology (Advanced ATM) for the long-term life prediction of polymer composites exposed to general loading of variable stress and temperature history is proposed in this paper.

1. The time and temperature dependence on the strength of polymer composites is controlled by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin to hold time-temperature superposition principle.
2. The formulation of long-term life under an actual loading can be shown by the multiplication of four terms. These terms are the static strength and its failure probability at room temperature to be independent of time and temperature, the power function of normalized viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin determined by the stress and temperature history, and the strength degradation caused by the damage linearly cumulated by the maximum stress, stress ratio and number of cycles on cyclic loading.
3. The formulations were applied to the flexural fatigue strengths of three kinds of CFRP laminates for marine use and the parameters in the formulations were determined.

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